

Energy performance of existing residential buildings in Europe: A novel approach combining energy with seismic retrofitting

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ABSTRACT

The current European building stock is ageing and requires significant renovation efforts to improve its energy performance and ensure structural safety. As part of the key actions of the European Green Deal, increased building renovations, a 'renovation wave', is needed to ensure that the ambitious EU energy saving and decarbonisation goals can be reached by 2030 and 2050, accordingly. To incentivise renovation further, integrating energy retrofitting with seismic strengthening is explored in this study. A combined energy and seismic retrofitting is investigated across twenty European cities with varied seismic hazard levels and different climatic conditions. Typical building types are defined both in terms of their energy and structural characteristics and are associated to the building population of each city. A monetary metric for combined assessments based on expected annual losses from energy costs and seismic losses is used and an optimum retrofitting scenario is identified. By means of the proposed renovation rate of 3%, a reduction of approximately 30% of primary energy use and CO₂ emissions may be achieved within a decade. Taking into account energy costs and costs related to structural damage it is found that a combined retrofitting scheme will reduce substantially the payback periods in moderate to high seismicity regions. In such locations the combined energy and seismic retrofitting is justified and proposed instead of the sole energy retrofitting typically applied today in existing buildings.

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1. Introduction and background

The impact of the existing building stock on the environment, with buildings being responsible for a large CO₂ emission share in the EU (36%) and heating and cooling accounting for 50% of the EU final energy consumption [1,2] is a topic of growing importance at international level. Such high values of CO₂ emissions and energy consumption can be essentially linked to the large number of old buildings in Europe, with a third of buildings over 50 years old [3]. Due to the lack or obsolete energy performance guidelines and seismic design codes at the time of their construction, but also due to ageing and degradation of the building materials, the energy performance of older buildings is inadequate. At the same time, their structural reliability is often also poor, meaning the safety of buildings is not always warranted, as highlighted by the vulnerability of the existing building stock to recent earthquakes [4–7].

With demolition and rebuilding neither being an economically viable nor an environmentally friendly solution at scale, renovation

and retrofit strategies are required to address the ageing building stock in developed countries of the world. The energy refurbishment of residential buildings can achieve high reductions in energy consumption [8,9], with the addition, for instance, of thermal insulation leading to reductions in heating needs by up to 70% [10]. Still over the last decade only 0.4–1.2 % of the EU's building stock was renovated yearly [11]. The final energy consumption across the EU in 2017 exceeded by 3.3% the annual target value needed to reach the 2020 target of 20% energy efficiency improvements [12]. To achieve the objective of reducing energy consumption by at least 32.5% by means of improvements in energy efficiency by 2030 [13], annual building renovation rates of 2–3% would need to be achieved [14]. The ambitious plans of the European Green Deal, emphasise the need for the EU and its Member States to engage in a 'renovation wave' of public and private buildings [15]. Until recently, the renovation of existing buildings was focusing either on solving structural safety problems or on increasing the energy performance. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) [2] was set-up as a framework for energy performance strategies, clearly indicating that besides reducing greenhouse gas emissions, fire safety and seismic risks which affect the lifetime of

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buildings should be addressed by Member States when planning long-term renovation strategies of buildings. Indeed, disregarding seismic risk and seismic retrofitting may cause misleading expectations on actual savings for an energy retrofitted building, as energy retrofitting alone does not lead to a reduction in seismic vulnerability and the energy retrofit may be lost due to an earthquake [16].

In recent years, researchers have raised and analysed the topic of combined seismic and energy retrofitting, assessing the benefits of eliminating seismic and energy performance deficiencies of existing buildings through a single intervention [17–21]. New methodologies are required for combined assessments of existing buildings and evaluating the potential benefits from combined interventions. A Sustainable Structural Design method, looking at life-cycle costs, as well as energy and seismic losses, was explored for new builds as well as renovation assessments [22,23]. Calvi et al. [24] proposed a joined assessment of energy efficiency and seismic resilience using financial decision-making variables (expected annual losses) and defining the ‘green and resilient indicator’ (GRI), which allows to classify a building’s seismic and energy performance, in an analogous way to building energy certificates with A to F ratings. Various integrated renovation approaches were investigated for case study buildings in Italy, and were found to always be more advantageous from a cost-benefit perspective than a separate seismic or energy approach.

To address the technical challenges regarding the implementation of combined retrofitting, different potential materials or solutions have been proposed. A possible approach for combining seismic and energy retrofitting may be the use of an exoskeleton [25,26] or double-skin solution [27] for integrating structural strengthening, energy performance upgrade and architectural renewal for RC buildings. Changing existing external wall facades with better performing materials is also proposed [27,28]. Composite materials such as textile reinforced mortars (TRM) may offer avenues for combined retrofitting, e.g. using thermal mortars reinforced by glass fibre textiles to improve mechanical properties of masonry walls or infills, while additionally reducing their thermal conductivity [29]. Similarly, using plasters for structural and energy upgrading has also been recently proposed [30]. Combining TRM with thermal insulation materials, was shown to be more effective from the strengthening point of view [31,32]. The economic feasibility of such a combined TRM and thermal insulation solution was evaluated for the case of RC buildings by Bournas [19] and Gkournelos et al. [33] by combining expected annual losses in terms of seismic losses and energy costs. It was shown that a significant reduction in payback period when considering a combined retrofit is achieved.

This study expands from previous work by assessing the benefits of combined energy and seismic retrofitting for the first time at the building stock level, including a variety of EU residential building typologies across different locations with a range of combinations of seismic hazard and climatic conditions. Representative existing buildings from various construction periods are selected and the target for energy and seismic retrofitting were determined for four characteristic climatic zones and five seismic zones, respectively, reflecting typical building characteristics from a thermal and structural point of view. A novel retrofit scheme combining thermal insulation and advanced composite materials for the building envelope is applied to reach the energy and structural performance targets after retrofitting. The buildings’ energy demand and seismic safety before and after retrofitting are assessed for the different climatic and seismic scenarios, leading to the first large-scale assessment of the building stock using a combined metric, namely expected annual loss. The effect of different renovation rates on the building stock is finally assessed through foresight studies for the chosen case study locations up to 2030.

2. Methodology

2.1. Case study locations

To explore the impact of the combined energy and seismic retrofitting, twenty European cities located in areas of different seismic hazard and climatic conditions were chosen as case study locations. Those cities are grouped in four different climatic and five seismic zones as illustrated in Fig. 1.

As shown in Table 1, the climatic zones were classified by heating degree-days (HDD), a weather-based index representing the difference between a base temperature and a day’s mean temperature. The base temperature represents the outdoor air temperature at which the indoor air does not need to be conditioned in order to meet indoor comfort. Using the ASHRAE method [34], a base temperature of 18°C is selected to calculate the HDD values for this study. The outdoor air temperature data is taken from EnergyPlus weather files generated from a period of climate record of typically 30 years [35]. The seismic zones were defined on the expected peak ground acceleration (PGA) for a return period of 475 years (10% exceedance in 50 years) [36]. Earthquakes induced by gas extraction in Groningen area were also considered by assigning a PGA value of 0.1 g [37].

2.2. Residential building stock and case study buildings

The residential sector constitutes the major share (75%) of the EU building stock [4]. In many European countries over half of the residential building stock was built before the 1970s and hence does not comply with modern energy efficiency and seismic safety requirements. Low to mid-rise stone and brick masonry buildings constitute the typical traditional buildings widespread in historical areas of Europe, with very limited construction of RC structures before 1945 [38]. Most mid-rise and high-rise buildings, in turn, were constructed after the 1960’s using reinforced concrete [39–41]. The highest construction rate of buildings was in 1960–1991 with a share of 45% of the total number of existing buildings in Europe. Multi-storey RC frames with masonry infills or precast RC panels represent the typical structure of such buildings, the first type having a high incidence in almost all Europe while the second one is predominant in Eastern Europe [3].

In order to assess the impact of combined seismic and energy retrofitting for the European building stock, representative building typologies need to be defined. In the literature, the classification of structures is typically different for describing the building stock based on its energy [42–48] and seismic performance [49–55]. Generally, the construction period, the main structural system or material (e.g. RC or masonry) and the geometric dimensions (e.g. number of storeys) are key parameters for both the energy and the seismic performance of buildings. As general consensus, buildings can be classified into low, medium and high-rise according to their number of storeys, grouped typically into 1–3, 4–6 and 6+ storeys,

Table 1
Matrix of case study locations by seismic risk (PGA) and climatic condition (HDD).

Zonation	Zone 1 HDD ≤ 1200	Zone 2 1200 < HDD ≤ 2200	Zone 3 2200 < HDD ≤ 3000	Zone 4 3000 < HDD ≤ 4000
PGA ≤ 0.05	Seville	Porto	Milan	Warsaw
0.05 < PGA ≤ 0.15	Faro	Bari	Belgrade	Bratislava/ Groningen
0.15 < PGA ≤ 0.25	Lisbon	Rome	Geneva	Bucharest
0.25 < PGA < 0.35	Athens	Thessaloniki	Perugia	Sofia
PGA ≥ 0.35	Larnaca	Istanbul	Potenza	/

Fig. 1. Map of case study locations categorised by seismic risk and climatic conditions.

respectively, for the European building stock [e.g.: 49,56–59]. In terms of energy performance, the U-values of envelope elements varies with age [60]. For the seismic design of structures, typically a distinction of no-code, pre-code and modern-code is made, which again classifies the buildings into different age groups [e.g.: 61].

The age groups chosen in this study are pre-1945, 1945–1960, 1961–1970, 1971–1989 and post-1989. These time periods are chosen to match major changes in building type (from masonry-dominated to RC-dominated construction), as well as in terms of changes in thermal [41] and seismic performance [62] due to updates or creation of code provisions. Broadly, in terms of seismic design level, no consideration was made before the 1950s, with moderate seismic design provisions in the 1960s and 1970s. The 1980s can be seen as a period of transition in Europe in which detailed or modern seismic codes were established throughout European countries [62,63]. To be conservative, this period of transition is still considered in the structures to be assessed and retrofitted.

Data on the building stock for each case study location is obtained by two main sources. On the one hand the number of dwellings or average useful floor space constructed by decade is obtained from the respective Census data of 2011 [64–66]. The building age from the Census data is shown Fig. 2 for each case study location. It can be seen that some cities have a building stock dominated by more modern construction (e.g. Istanbul or Thessaloniki), while other cities, in particular Italian ones (e.g. Perugia, Potenza, but also Groningen or Geneva) have a large proportion between 20–30% of pre-1945 structures, classified as low and mid-rise masonry buildings.

On the other hand the proportion of construction type is taken from the NERA project [38], from which data on building height was aggregated and allowed for a discretization of buildings into low to high-rise infilled RC buildings and low to mid-rise masonry

buildings, respectively. As shown in Table 2, for the masonry buildings, low-rise and mid-rise buildings with stone and clay brick masonry as materials are defined. In the case of the RC buildings low (two storeys), mid (four storeys) and high-rise (eight storeys) structures were defined. The floor area of 8×18 m is chosen to be globally representative, as the selected buildings are theoretical in nature and their geometrical characteristics represent somewhat of an average of the building stock, similar to other large-scale studies on the building stock [e.g.: 67–69]. Note that an opening percentage of 15% of wall area per storey is assumed. This corresponds to a 1.2×2.1 m door or two 0.9×1.45 m windows for two bays. Typical traditional masonry buildings do not have a constant storey-height along their height and respectively the size of openings decreases. Lower storeys tend to have a higher inter-storey height than typical RC structures. An average height of 4 m for the ground floor is assumed here and a window dimensions equal to 1.0×1.90 m, resulting in glazing 18.3% for low-rise and mid-rise masonry buildings.

The relative proportion of the building types in terms of their building height or material (stone or brick masonry) aggregated from the NERA project is shown in Table 3.

Among the building envelope components, the walls and windows typically represent the major share of the overall energy loss [70], so this study focuses on these elements. Considering the extensive variations over the years and from country to country, five different typical external wall types were selected representing the different time periods, as illustrated in Table 4.

Masonry buildings are considered the predominant typology before 1945. The characteristics of their external walls have been based on seismic vulnerability and energy studies of existing masonry buildings [e.g.: 6,68,71–73]. While typically the thickness of the walls in masonry buildings varies along the height especially for mid-rise structures, here, average values have been considered, with 30 cm for solid brick walls and 45 cm for stone walls. Stone

Fig. 2. Proportion of built floor area by period of construction in the selected locations [64–66].

Table 2
Parameters of the case study buildings

Structural material	Masonry		Reinforced Concrete		
	Low-Rise stone or brick	Mid-Rise brick	Low-Rise	Mid-Rise	High-Rise
Sketch					
Plan	8m x 18m	8m x 18m	8m x 18m	8m x 18m	8m x 18m
Tot. floor area	m ² 288	576	288	576	1152
No. of storeys	2	4	2	4	8
Storey height	m 4 (first) / 3.30	4 (first) / 3.10	3	3	3
Total height	m 9.60	15.90	6	12	24
Windows	m ² 66.10	124.20	40.60	86.42	178.06
Exterior doors	m ² 5.80	11.60	5.04	5.04	5.04
Glazing	% 18.30	18.30	15	15	15

walls are generally multi-leaf and an assumption of 60% stone and 40% mortar is made.

For the RC buildings, the thickness and materials of the external walls were chosen in accordance with a literature survey on infill wall dimensions in the countries of interest [e.g.: 40,74–76]. Solid clay bricks used for single leaf walls are more common in buildings, dating before 1959, in various European countries such as Romania, Germany, Greece and Italy. Starting with 1950's or 1960's, hollow clay bricks began to be used in single leaf walls, and later double leaf and cavity walls ensuring better thermal and sound insulation. Hollow clay bricks with vertical holes have higher incidence in Italy and Romania while horizontally perforated bricks are

frequently found in Portugal, Greece and Turkey. Usually, the total thickness of the cavity wall is about 30 cm and the cavity thickness is commonly 5–10 cm. To achieve a better thermal performance in many buildings built after the 1970's or 1980's, thermal insulation materials such as mineral wool were inserted in the cavity, as for the post-1989 building envelope. The U-values in Table 4 are compared to the range of U-values of external wall elements in EU residential buildings based on the data collected in [41] for the respective time periods. Details on the envelope materials are presented in Tables A.1–A10 of Appendix A.

A key parameter in terms of assessing the thermal performance of buildings is the thermal transmittance of its envelope elements

Table 3
Relative proportion of building heights within Masonry and infilled RC buildings per location, aggregated from [38]

Location	Masonry buildings			Infilled RC buildings		
	Low-rise stone	Low-rise brick	Mid-rise brick	Low-Rise	Mid-Rise	High-Rise
Faro	14%	78%	8%	93%	4%	2%
Larnaca	42%	53%	5%	88%	10%	3%
Lisbon	14%	78%	8%	93%	4%	2%
Seville	25%	69%	7%	82%	13%	5%
Athens	20%	73%	7%	88%	10%	3%
Porto	14%	78%	8%	93%	4%	2%
Rome	7%	84%	8%	82%	18%	0%
Bari	7%	84%	8%	82%	18%	0%
Thessaloniki	16%	77%	8%	88%	10%	3%
Istanbul	28%	65%	7%	74%	23%	2%
Perugia	7%	84%	8%	82%	18%	0%
Milan	7%	84%	8%	82%	18%	0%
Potenza	7%	84%	8%	82%	18%	0%
Belgrade	16%	77%	8%	88%	10%	3%
Geneva	7%	84%	8%	82%	18%	0%
Bucharest	1%	90%	9%	60%	20%	20%
Sofia	1%	90%	9%	60%	20%	20%
Bratislava	9%	83%	8%	97%	3%	0%
Groningen	7%	85%	8%	95%	5%	0%
Warsaw	22%	71%	7%	94%	6%	0%

Table 4
Envelope characteristics for the different time periods

Period	Pre-1945	1945-1959	1960-1969	1970 – 1989	Post-1989
Material	Stone or brick masonry	solid clay brick masonry	hollow clay brick masonry	hollow clay brick masonry	hollow clay brick masonry and thermal insulation
Detail	Multi-leaf wall	Multi-leaf wall	Single leaf wall	Cavity wall	Cavity wall
Sketch					
U (W/m ² K)	1.30 - 2.25	1.77	0.97	0.79	0.35 - 0.75
EU-range[41]	0.9 - 2.5	0.9 - 2.4	0.5 - 2.1	0.4 - 1.6	0.23 - 0.85

(U-value in W/m²/K). The U'-values, i.e. the U-value considering any thermal bridges, are shown for the selected envelope types, were calculated using Eq. (1) after evaluating the effect of different thermal bridges in HEAT2 [77], a two dimensional heat transfer simulation software following ISO 10211 [78] and ISO 10077-2 standards [79]:

$$U' = U + \frac{\sum \psi \cdot l}{A} \quad [W/(m^2K)] \quad (1)$$

Where U is the thermal transmittance of the building envelope element (exterior walls), A the area of the building envelope element (in m²) and $\sum \psi \cdot l$ the sum of all products of thermal bridge ψ -values (thermal transmittance of the linear thermal bridge in W/(mK)) and the lengths of thermal bridges. The ψ -values corresponding to the internal dimensions of the thermal bridge cross-section were considered. For masonry buildings, the majority of linear thermal bridges are generated by the geometry of the build-

Table 5
Main thermal bridges of the 1945–59 RC building

Location of thermal bridge	Corner	Walls intersection	Wall- floor intersection
HEAT2 simulation			
ψ (W/mK)	0.348	0.215	0.601
Location of thermal bridge	Wall- roof intersection	Windows horizontal section	Windows vertical section -up
HEAT2 simulation			
ψ (W/mK)	0.673	0.201	0.609

ings, such as external masonry walls intersections (corners), internal masonry wall intersections with external masonry wall, while only a few are generated by combining different thermal conductive materials such as wooden floor intersection with external masonry wall and wooden window frame and masonry wall connection. For the RC buildings, the relevant thermal bridges are caused by combining materials of different thermal conductivity, i.e. RC elements with the masonry infills. Indicatively, the main thermal bridges identified in the 1945–59 RC building are presented in Table 5.

It can be observed that higher ψ -values are generated by wall-roof and wall-floor intersection and in the upper part of the windows, but generally the highest impact in the recalculation of the walls U-value is generated by the wall - floor intersection due to the length of this thermal bridge type, especially in the case of mid and high-rise buildings.

2.3. Combined retrofitting approach

The concurrent seismic and energy retrofitting concept is investigated by considering materials addressing both issues when designing the retrofit scheme of the walls, namely TRM jacketing combined with thermal insulation, as illustrated in Fig. 3. This solution consists of a high strength lightweight bi-directional textile composite made from carbon, glass or basalt fibres for seismic retrofitting of both structural and non-structural members. Bonding of the strengthening material to the building envelope is realised by inorganic cement-based mortars, resulting in a TRM composite and additionally provides fire resistance if the selected thermal insulation has moderate fire resistance.

An additional insulation material is then integrated with the seismic reinforcement to improve the energy performance. This insulation layer in Fig. 3 may be mineral wool or polystyrene, which have λ -values around 35 mW/mK [80]. Alternatively, a variety of other materials may be used, with several reviews of materials available in the literature [80–87]. When considering an integrated retrofit solution, fire resistance is also crucial, hence solutions with good fire ratings such as mineral wool insulation or more advanced solutions such as vacuum insulation panels (VIP) may be particularly beneficial.

The intervention concept is similar to existing separate seismic or energy retrofitting solutions on building envelopes, where the externally applied reinforcement or insulation material are bonded to concrete or masonry envelope surfaces using mortars. The com-

Fig. 3. Combined seismic and energy retrofit.

binated retrofit allows to achieve both the required safety and energy performance, with one single intervention, hence keeping the overall cost low by dramatically reducing the labour cost.

2.3.1. Energy performance target

To achieve an adequate energy performance in existing buildings, thermal insulation can be seen as the easiest and most cost-effective solution [60]. While energy renovation encompasses a variety of interventions [88,89], including changes in HVAC system, adding renewable energy sources or shading devices, in this study, the renovation targets are defined in terms of the U-value of the envelope elements in order to reduce transmission heat losses. National energy performance legislations typically recommend U-values for different envelope elements (exterior walls, windows, roofs) to be achieved by new-built or renovated structures. The values for all case study locations are shown in Table 6 and are used to define U-value targets for the retrofit solution. In countries where U-value requirements for retrofitting of existing buildings are not available, the requirements for new built structures were taken, as illustrated in the last column of Table 6.

Table 6
U-values target in each case-study location.

Zone	City	U-values [W/m ² K]								New built/existing*
		Walls		Roof	Floor on ground		Windows			
1	Larnaca	0.85	0.75	0.75	0.61	0.75	0.68	3.80	3.10	N+R
	Lisbon	0.80		0.70		0.70		2.80		N
	Athens	0.50		0.45		0.45		3.00		N
	Seville	0.82		0.45		0.82		3.10		N+R
	Faro	0.80		0.70		0.70		2.80		N
2	Bari	0.40	0.50	0.38	0.42	0.42	0.46	2.60	2.52	N
	Porto	0.70		0.60		0.50		2.40		N
	Rome	0.36		0.32		0.36		2.40		N
	Salonnik	0.45		0.40		0.40		2.80		N
	Istanbul	0.60		0.40		0.60		2.40		N+R
3	Perugia	0.34	0.40	0.30	0.33	0.33	0.39	2.20	2.07	N
	Milan	0.34		0.30		0.33		2.20		N
	Potenza	0.36		0.32		0.36		2.40		N
	Belgrade	0.40		0.40		0.40		1.50		N+R
	Geneva	N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A		-
4	Bucharest	0.56	0.35	0.20	0.22	0.22	0.30	1.30	1.40	N
	Groningen	0.20		0.20		0.29		1.65		N+R
	Sofia	0.35		0.28		0.40		1.70		N
	Bratislava	0.32		0.20		0.40		1.40		N
	Warsaw	0.23		0.20		0.25		1.10		N+R

* N- requirements for new buildings N+R – same requirements for both new and retrofitted buildings

In order to homogenize the energy performance of buildings placed in locations grouped in the same zone, a retrofit U-value target per zone for each envelope element was defined based on the values of the individual locations in the same zone. For instance, the chosen U-values and corresponding R-values (1/U) for exterior walls are 0.75 W/m²K (R-value = 1.33 m²K/W) for Zone 1, 0.50 (R = 2.00) for Zone 2, 0.40 (R = 2.50) for Zone 3 and 0.35 (R = 2.85) for Zone 4. As the typical U-values for walls in the EU vary with location and time periods, different levels of intervention would hence be required to achieve the required U-value of the structures, depending on their age and type of construction. For the buildings considered in this study (see Section 2.2), the U-value reductions for the walls were ranging from 41% (from 1.27 to 0.75 W/m²K for a 1970's RC building in zone 1) up to 84% (from 2.24 to 0.35 W/m²K for a pre 1920's stone masonry building placed in zone 4).

In addition to changes in the U-value of exterior walls, the windows were improved by means of airtight frames and glass with low solar heat gain coefficient (SHGC) of 0.55. Replacing the existing windows has substantial effects on decreasing the infiltration heat losses by increasing the overall airtightness of the building. Therefore, the number of air changes was decreased from 1.0 to 0.60 h⁻¹ corresponding to moderate shielded buildings with medium airtightness [90].

2.3.2. Seismic performance target

The buildings selected in this study are grouped according to their ages and can hence be related to a certain level of seismic design of their time of construction. For the older unreinforced masonry (URM) and RC structures, (i) no seismic design is considered, an assumption valid for across all European cities. For the 1960–69 and 1970–89 structures, (ii) low and (iii) medium levels of seismic design code are assumed, respectively. For modern structures the assumption of a (iv) high-level of seismic design is taken. As a large and inhomogeneous building stock across multiple locations is hence addressed in this study, it is not possible to design a specific retrofit for reducing the vulnerability of all the different structures. Instead, in accordance with the framework of performance-based earthquake engineering (PBEE) [91], a target performance to be achieved by the retrofitted structures is defined.

Similarly to choosing an energy retrofit improving the envelope U-values from their existing state to meet modern U-value requirements, the target for seismic strengthening is often taken to be that of modern structures with a high level of seismic design [92].

Using TRM as a retrofit material, has been shown to achieve large improvements in seismic performance in various experimental studies on masonry walls or masonry-infilled RC frames, e.g. summarised by the authors in [93,94,119], respectively. The relation between type and thickness of TRM application has been explored analytically in another recent study [95], but generally, experimental evidence with retrofits of 1 or 2 layers of glass, carbon or basalt TRM for individual frames has shown to improve the seismic capacity by 10% up to 100%. For instance, up to two-fold increases in seismic load capacity were obtained even with two layers of basalt-TRM [96]. A retrofit using two layers of glass-TRM at ground level and one layer at the upper storeys described in previous experimental work on a three-storey RC frame, ensured a strength increase of 54.2% and improved the evolution of damage significantly, avoiding a soft-storey failure [97]. Furthermore, for masonry piers which are more brittle, the seismic capacity can be profoundly enhanced by as much as 8 and 20 times for walls loaded in-plane or out-of-plane, respectively, applying one or more layers of composite textile [e.g.: 98,99].

Based on this evidence a rather conservative assumption is made: the retrofitted buildings were not assumed to achieve the behaviour of modern high-code buildings, but instead an improvement in performance of two categories in terms of seismic design level is assumed after receiving seismic retrofitting (as shown in Table 7). Therefore, RC buildings with no-seismic design achieved a medium level of seismic design after retrofit (from (i) to (iii) and from (ii) to (iv), etc.). For the URM buildings the performance achieved after the TRM-retrofitting is assumed to be that of medium (for stone walls) or high-code (for brick walls) reinforced masonry (RBM) structures.

2.4. Building energy performance simulation

The energy performance of the case-study buildings was assessed by means of dynamic energy simulations in EnergyPlus [100], namely by calculating the energy demand for space heating (HED) and cooling (CED) per conditioned floor area (kWh/m²)

Table 7
Target seismic design level of the seismic retrofit scheme.

Age	Pre-1945	Pre-1945	1945-1959	1960-1969	1970-1989	Post-1989
Material	Stone	Brick	RC	RC	RC	RC
Seismic design level	URM (stone)	URM (brick)	No code	Low	Medium	High
Target design level	RBM (medium)	RBM (high)	Medium	High	High	N/A

Table 8
Main parameters of the energy simulations.

Simulation parameters	Value	Unit
Air infiltration rate	1.0 h ⁻¹	ACH
Heating set-point	20	°C
Cooling set-point	25	°C
Occupants heat gains	4	W/m ²
Artificial lighting load	8	W/m ²
Hot water heat gains	3	W/m ²
Electric equipment heat gains	10	W/m ²

across the different locations. The main simulation parameters are summarized in Table 8. Compared to monthly and seasonal steady-state methods, where the heating and cooling season have fix lengths before starting the calculation, in dynamic simulations, heating and cooling are a result of the dynamic effects of the external climate and the behaviour of the building. Climate data for all locations was derived from the International Weather for Energy Calculations (IWEC) weather files, which give hourly weather data recorded for periods up to 18 years [35]. Annual energy balance simulations were performed for each building using a value of ten time steps per hour, meaning a 6 min time step.

An ideal heating and cooling system was considered and the set point temperatures recommended in ISO 13790 [90] were selected, namely 25 °C for cooling and 20 °C for heating, respectively. Each floor of the buildings is defined by a single thermal zone. According to ISO 13,790, thermal zone division is not necessary when the set-point temperatures of the zones differ not more than 4K. Since all the case study buildings are considered fully residential buildings, all thermal zones were conditioned to uphold the same heating and cooling set-point temperatures, except for the attics, which are considered to be unconditioned. The envelope elements of the buildings (slab on ground, roof, and exterior walls) were defined as heat transfer surfaces while the interior elements (floors, partition walls) were defined as heat storage surfaces. For each building, surface a boundary condition was assigned: outdoor (sun and wind exposed or not), ground or zone. All surfaces were described using centerline dimensions. Building elements were then assigned to all surfaces by adding layers of materials. The windows were defined describing the entire glazing system using simple performance parameters, namely the U-value of the system and the Solar Heat Gain Coefficient (SHGC). For the sake of simplicity, no shading devices were considered for any case study building.

Internal heat gains generated by occupants were considered by assuming an average activity level of 140 W/person [100] and a design level of 36 m²/ person The heat flow rate resulted in approximately 4 W/m². The occupants' heat gains were generated based on a typical occupancy schedule (Fig. 4). The heat gains from interior lighting were evaluated on a watts/area calculation method basis. The lighting design level was assumed to be 8 W/m² and the lighting schedule was based on the occupancy schedule, i.e. lighting needs change between the morning and evening when occupants wake up and leave the house or return home, respectively. The electric equipment was assumed with a maximum design level of 10 W/m² and the occupancy schedule. Finally, the heat gains

Fig. 4. Occupancy and lighting hourly schedule

generated from domestic hot water circulation pipes in bathrooms and kitchens, which are assumed to be vertical and without thermal insulation, as it is typical for older buildings, were also averaged over the entire conditioned area. The heat gains are estimated with a value of 40 W/m for an average pipe length of 10 m (e.g.: 2 bathrooms, 2 kitchens) per floor area (144 m²), adding up to a value of 3 W/m² [101].

The building geometries and envelope material characteristics described in Table 2 and Table 4, respectively, are implemented in the models. As older structures are considered, the inadequacy in their envelopes due to thermal bridges and air infiltration (air leakages) through cracks also need to be considered [102]. Moreover, ageing of the materials was considered by increasing the conventional thermal conductivity [103]. In order to account for thermal bridging in the building energy modelling (BEM), the U'-value, i.e. the thermal transmittance of envelope elements including the thermal bridges was calculated according to Eq. 1, and then implemented by adjusting the thermal conductivity of the exterior wall layer to match the calculated U'-value. In this way the thermal mass effect defined by density, specific heat and thickness is preserved and the increased thermal conductivity due to the presence thermal bridges is also considered.

The natural ventilation and infiltration losses in the energy balance of the case study buildings were considered by the design flow rate calculation method based on the number of air changes per hour (ACH). No mechanical ventilation system was considered. The rate of air changes was evaluated based on ISO 13790 [90] data for naturally ventilated multi-family buildings. All the case study buildings were considered to be moderate shielded with more than one exposed façade and having low air tightness therefore obtaining an air change rate of 1.0 h⁻¹ before retrofit. The low airtightness of the case study buildings is assumed based on their age, old buildings usually having leaky windows frames and cracks in the envelope elements especially in the case of the buildings located in seismic areas. This assumption will be evaluated further in an experimental campaign currently under preparation.

2.5. Costs and primary energy factors

2.5.1. Energy costs and savings

Heating and cooling energy demands and energy use were obtained from the energy simulation. It is noted that, system losses, auxiliary energy, hot water and lighting energy use are conservatively assumed not to change between the existing and retrofitted states. As the interest in this study is assessing the change in energy use due to retrofitting, the primary energy use and associated equivalent-CO₂ emissions are calculated from heating and cooling demands. The heating and cooling demands are multiplied by the respective total primary energy factors (f_{Ptot}) and factor for equivalent operational CO₂ emissions ($k_{\text{CO}_2\text{e}}$ in g/kWh). These are obtained by multiplying the primary energy factors and equivalent operational CO₂ emission factors of different energy sources from ISO 52000-1 [104] with the relative proportions of different energy sources used for heating and cooling based on the energy mix of the relevant countries from the 2015 residential profiles [1]. For the years after 2015, the change in energy mix up to 2020 and 2030 is assumed to follow the scenario described in [105], leading to recalculation of f_{Ptot} and $k_{\text{CO}_2\text{e}}$ for the periods up to 2020 and 2030. The data used for each city can be found in Table B.1 of Appendix B.

To assess the financial impact of energy retrofitting, energy costs are transformed into estimated annual losses (EAL_E). As shown in Eq. 2, the EAL_E is obtained by dividing the heating and cooling energy costs per m² of each building type by the estimated building prices per m² at each location. The energy costs are calculated based on the annual heating and cooling energy consumptions multiplied by the energy prices in the selected case study locations from EUROSTAT [106,107]. The building prices per m² are evaluated from [108]. Again, the data used for each city can be found in Table B.1 of Appendix B.

$$EAL_E = \frac{\text{annual heating + cooling cost}}{\text{total building value}} [\%] \quad (2)$$

The annual energy savings due to retrofitting are then expressed as the difference in EAL_E before and after retrofitting, again as a percentage of the total building value. Note that the building value would potentially increase as a consequence of retrofitting. As this is difficult to precisely quantify, it is conservatively ignored from the analysis.

2.5.2. Seismic loss estimation

To evaluate the combined benefit of an integrated energy and seismic retrofitting approach, the additional costs and savings for seismic retrofitting were also considered herein. The expected annual loss due to seismic events (EAL_S) was evaluated in line with the PEER performance based earthquake engineering (PBEE) methodology [91]. Rather than using a deterministic approach with specific mechanical characteristics of the building materials, a probabilistic approach is taken, i.e. in order to consider the typical spread of material characteristics for the different construction periods.

The procedure used to define the EAL_S is summarised in Fig. 5. First, fragility functions (Fig. 5a) are used to determine the probability of reaching a certain level of damage (or damage state DS) for a certain level of earthquake intensity, presented in terms of PGA to be compatible with the intensity of seismic hazard at each location in Fig. 1. Typical fragility functions with five DS (ranging from 'no damage' to 'collapse') for the chosen RC [49] and unreinforced masonry [109] buildings were selected from the literature according to their age, number of storeys (low, mid- and high-rise) and building material (stone, brick). The age of the buildings was associated to the respective seismic design level of the construction period, and four seismic design levels were hence assumed: (i)

Fig. 5. Summary of procedure for EAL_S calculation per building per location

no design, (ii) low, (iii) medium and (iv) high level of seismic design. The vulnerability of the seismically retrofitted structures with TRM is defined according to the targeted performance, as defined in Section 2.3.2, with the assumption of target seismic performance for the retrofitted buildings, summarised in Table 7.

The parameters needed to construct the fragility curves for the different building categories are shown in Tables B.2.–B.5. of Appendix B, presenting the mean μ and standard deviation σ for the respective lognormal cumulative distribution functions of probability of reaching each of the five damage states against the intensity measure, in this case peak ground acceleration (PGA in g).

Following from the fragility functions, the specific damage levels are associated to monetary loss as a fraction of the existing building value, by means of a damage-to-loss function specific for masonry and RC structures. The values for the damage-to-loss functions from [49] are shown in Table B.6. of Appendix B. Note that this loss is based on the cost of repair for the specific damage states and is always less than or equal to the replacement cost, i.e. the value of the building. Other losses that can be associated to earthquakes, such as human losses and the social impact are however not considered, as the scope of this study focuses only on buildings and the assumption of repair costs alone renders more conservative results. The fragility curves (Fig. 5a) and damage-to-loss functions (Fig. 5b) are then combined to give the vulnerability curve (Fig. 5c) of the specific building type, i.e. the monetary loss (as a percentage of the building value) vs. the selected intensity measure (PGA).

To assess the annual losses, the annual probability of exceedance (PE) of PGA values needs to be defined based on the seismic hazard at each location. Eurocode 8 [96] suggests that the annual rate of exceedance $H(a_{gR})$ of a reference PGA (a_{gR}) can be assumed to vary with a_{gR} according to Eq. (3)

$$H(a_{gR}) \cong k_0 \cdot a_{gR}^{-k} \quad (3)$$

The proposed value for k in Eq. (3) is 3 [110] and k_0 can be computed based on the a_{gR} that corresponds to a probability of ex-

Fig. 6. Analysis of the energy renovation target effectiveness.

2.5.3. Combined losses and retrofit costs

Then the combined losses are defined as in [19] namely $EAL_C = EAL_E + EAL_S$ and the savings due to retrofit are given as the difference of the initial annual losses ($EAL_{C,i}$) and the losses after retrofit application ($EAL_{C,r}$), as in Eq. 4:

$$\Delta EAL_C = EAL_{C,i} - EAL_{C,r} \quad [\%] \quad (4)$$

It is worth noting that the cost estimations in this study are to be taken as preliminary in nature, and the values are not expected to reflect necessarily financial realities. Instead, the costs are taken indicatively in order to evaluate trends. Retrofit costs per m² are defined for the energy retrofit and seismic retrofit based on averages obtained from multiple studies for various countries, including Greece and Italy [17,33,111–116]. To account for the geographic differences in retrofit costs, the broad assumption is made that the costs can be weighted for the different locations using the European Construction Costs Index [117]. The cost for energy retrofitting considers thermal insulation and the cost of replacing windows, and, like the cost of the seismic retrofit using glass-TRM [97], was assessed in a previous study [19]. Note that despite the simplified assumption for the TRM retrofit cost, the cost of using a layer of TRM less or an additional layer would not practically affect the price, due to the low cost of glass and basalt textiles compared to working hours and building preparation, which in turn are independent of the number of textile layers. The cost of the combined intervention is estimated to be 25% cheaper than energy and the seismic retrofit applied separately [33]. As mentioned in Section 2.3, this is due to the integration of seismic and energy retrofitting materials leading to reduced labour costs, scaffolding etc., which are only paid once, rather than at two separate occasions. Indicatively, the assumed retrofit costs used for Italy are

ceedance of 10% in 50 years, i.e. the values in Fig. 1. For instance, Lisbon has an expected PGA of 0.25 g for a return period of 475 years (10% exceedance in 50 years). The function of annual probability of exceedance of a certain PGA derived from Eq. 3 and presented in Fig. 5(d) it is then combined with the intensity to loss curve (Fig. 5c) to build a curve of annual probability of exceedance of loss (in % of building value). As shown in Fig. 5(e), the expected annual seismic loss (EAL_S) is then the integral of this function. This procedure is repeated for all building typologies (i.e. material, age and building height) before and after retrofitting and for each location (i.e for the individual seismic hazard of the site).

Fig. 7. Average total annual energy demand per building type across all locations.

Fig. 8. Average reduction in total annual energy demand due to retrofit per building type in each zone.

taken to be 200 €/m² for the energy retrofit alone, 160 €/m² for the seismic retrofit with TRM and 270 €/m² for the combined retrofit.

Finally, as proposed in [19], the indicative payback period of the retrofitting interventions can be calculated as the ratio of the assumed costs of the retrofit (with respect to the non-retrofitted building) to the annual cost savings in Eq. 5:

$$t_{\text{payback}} = \frac{\text{Retrofit cost}_k / \text{building value}}{\Delta \text{EAL}_k} [\text{years}] \quad (5)$$

Where k corresponds to the respective values of the energy, seismic or combined retrofit, depending on the evaluation.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Energy retrofit target analysis

To assess the effectiveness of the chosen target U-values of each zone, energy simulations were performed in selected cities (Larnaca, Istanbul, Milan, and Warsaw), representing each of the four climatic zones, for increasing thermal insulation thickness for a generic building with walls with an R-value of 0.495 m²K/W. The thickness of the thermal insulation layer, i.e. mineral wool with $\lambda = 40$ mW/mK, was gradually increased from no thermal insulation to 30 cm. Consequently, the R-value increased from the initial R-value of the walls up to a final R-value of 8.00 m²K/W. The corresponding U-values are 2.02 and 0.125 W/ m²K, respectively.

The heating energy demand of the analysed building against the thermal insulation thickness and corresponding R-value is shown in Fig. 6. The energy demand does not linearly decrease with thermal insulation thickness and for larger thicknesses the reduction in energy demand is less pronounced. As can be seen, the average

code required R-value (reciprocal of U-value in Table 6) for exterior walls can be obtained for a small thickness of thermal insulation (e.g. 5–10 cm for zones 2–4 and only 3 cm for zone 1). An increased thickness of the retrofit layer would not lead to significantly larger energy savings and would hence not justify higher retrofit costs. Therefore, this analysis justifies the use of the R-values (or U-values in Table 6) selected as target for the retrofitted buildings (see Section 2.3).

3.2. Energy demand of existing and retrofitted buildings

The results in terms of total energy demands, i.e. the combined heating and cooling demand, for all building types in need for retrofit across the four climatic zones are summarised in Fig. 7. Each climatic zone consists of five cities of varying seismicity but similar climatic conditions. Still as the cities in each zone present differences in their annual weather data, the variation in energy demand including minimum and maximum values, as well as the average energy demand for each building are hence given.

As it was expected, it can be observed that the oldest structures (pre-1945), i.e. the stone masonry buildings, consume the most energy across all locations. In turn, the more modern structures (1970–89), with improved U-values performed the best. In the colder regions (zone 4), the highest total energy demands can be observed, with average energy demands doubled compared to the hotter zones for all the different building types. The obtained energy demands are reasonable compared to average annual energy demands in the EU-28 to be around 175 kWh/m² in 2014 [39], which contain a large number of post-1990's structures.

Overall a trend of higher energy demand per floor area is observed for low-rise structures compared to high-rise buildings,

Fig. 9. Estimated annual energy cost savings and payback periods per building type in each zone. Note: the red squares indicate the payback period for the energy retrofit.

which is as expected due to different envelope area and floor area ratios, with high rise-building being more compact. Mid-rise masonry buildings, consume less energy compared to their RC counterparts (Fig. 7).

When applying the respective retrofitting solutions for the different zones, large decreases in total energy demand are obtained for all building types, as shown in Fig. 8. It can be seen that the highest reductions take place for older low-rise buildings (average 78%) and for the buildings of zone 4 (average improvements close to 75%), whereas for zone 1 the lowest reduction in total energy demands is observed. For mid-rise masonry and high-rise RC structures, the improvement in energy demand is between 37 and 45% for zone 1, compared to reductions close to 70% for low rise buildings. In the colder zones, the differences in reduction potential between lower and higher rise structures are less pronounced.

The reduction in energy demand for each building can be correlated with energy cost savings (see Eq. 2), and the estimated savings per year normalised by the building value are shown in Fig. 9. Together with the assumed costs of energy retrofitting in each case study location, the payback periods of the retrofit were calculated using Eq. 5. As the energy costs in Europe do not vary in the same way as building values and construction costs, large variations in estimated annual savings (ΔEAL_E) can be found across the different locations within the same zones. In zone 1, while the savings in energy demand are the lowest, the average cost savings are the highest and very low payback periods between five years for older masonry structures and 25 years for high rise RC buildings are obtained. This is mainly attributable to the relatively high heating energy costs and electricity costs for cooling in the countries of Zone 1 (Cyprus, Greece, Spain and Portugal) together with lower real estate values compared to the EU-average. The ratio of savings to building value is hence very high in these locations. For Zone 4,

the highest energy savings are made, and with respect to Zones 2 and 3, larger cost savings are observed. Payback periods of around 10–20 years are hence obtained, while these are closer to 15–35 years in Zone 2 and 10–25 years in Zone 3. Lowest payback periods are observed in low-rise structures and older structures for which the highest energy savings are obtained. Compare to other studies for Italian low and mid-rise buildings, similar payback periods are calculated [24,33]. The effect of combined seismic and energy retrofitting on the payback periods is studied in Section 3.4.

It is important to add that low and mid-rise buildings are the most common building typologies in Europe, hence their energy retrofitting could result in large savings in energy use. The impact of various renovation strategies on a city level can be assessed, when combining the obtained energy demands for all building typologies and their relative distribution within the building stocks of the case study locations.

3.3. Long-term energy renovation impact

To assess the long-term energy renovation impact, first a projection for 2020 is made based on the available data for 2011, since no updated building stock data is available for the last decade. Using the obtained energy consumption for 2011, the impact of different renovation rates is then projected up to 2030 by using the data obtained from the building energy performance simulations. The effect of four different renovation scenarios is assessed across the case-study locations. This is of interest, as the EPBD requires EU member states to establish their national long-term renovation strategies for the building stock. The effect of the renovation scenarios is evaluated with respect to the assumed primary energy use in 2020. To obtain the forecasted energy use in the year of evaluation (2020) from the established case studies, a 1% renova-

Fig. 10. Reduction in primary energy use for all zones between 2011 and 2020.

tion rate per year is assumed since the date of the Census (2011). While this rate consists of a broad assumption, a more detailed distribution of the renovation rates across different locations, years and building types is not available. The assumption can however be deemed adequate as the renovation rate across all case study location was between 0.4–1.2% in 2014 [11] and is at 1.2% across the EU in 2018 [14]. As shown in Fig. 10, assuming a renovation

of 1% between 2011 and 2020 in all case study locations, average reductions in primary energy between 7% and 12% are obtained by 2020. Note that the shaded areas show the spread in reduction between the different cities of each zone.

After the year of evaluation, three scenarios are assumed: keeping the rate of renovation as it is (1% - 'current'), increasing it to 2% ('increased') or reaching the target 3% ('target'), i.e. the average rate recommended in the EPBD [2] and more recently by the EU Green Deal [15]. A last scenario is added, looking at keeping the same 3% target renovation rate, but starting by renovating the oldest buildings first before moving to buildings from more recent times. This latter scenario will be referred to as 'optimal' scenario both in terms of reduction of energy demands and possible seismic damage, as the more deficient buildings are renovated first. The reduction in primary energy up to 2030 compared to the evaluation year 2020 is shown in Fig. 11. The average reduction is shown by the solid line and the range across the five cities in each zone is shown by the respective shaded area.

Large reduction in primary energy use of the building stock between 20 and 30% can be seen by 2030 across all zones for the target (3%) and optimal (3%) renovation strategies. If the current renovation rate is kept, the reduction is merely one third of these values. With the 2% increased rate, by 2030 a maximum reduction of 20% compared to 2020 is obtained for the considered building stock, however the range of reduction can be as low as 14%.

To relate the obtained results with the EU Council's promoted target of cutting emissions by 30% by 2030 due to energy efficiency measures in the residential sector [14], equivalent CO₂ emissions are calculated based on the obtained primary energy consumption as described in Section 2.5. The reduction in equivalent CO₂ emissions by 2030 is mapped in Fig. 12 for the optimal renovation

Fig. 11. Reduction in primary energy use for all zones between 2020 and 2030 with four different renovation strategies.

Fig. 12. Reduction in CO₂-emissions by 2030 after implementation of an optimal renovation strategy.

strategy. It can be observed that the target for 2030 may indeed be reached in most locations-zones if the optimal renovation rate of 3% is implemented. Instead, with the current (1%) renovation rate, only 10–20% of CO₂ emission reduction can be obtained. It worth's noting that an additional reduction in CO₂ emissions is further expected (albeit not considered herein) due to seismic retrofitting, as repair and reconstruction works after seismic events are reduced.

If this optimal renovation strategy was implemented for the building stock of all case study locations, the impact on the average heating energy demand of the building stock can be seen Fig. 13 for all cities. The average annual heating energy demand per city for the current building stock and the building stock in 2030 after applying the 3% renovation rate since 2020 is shown. The average heating energy demand for a fully retrofitted building stock is also indicated for reference, which practically corresponds to all buildings performing like new ones. When all buildings are retrofitted, the performance of the building stock is more homogenous across all locations. By 2030, a significantly reduced energy demand can hence be obtained and the variation across the different European cities substantially decreased. For some cities with a large proportion of modern buildings (with close to 50% built after 1990), e.g. Istanbul, Larnaca or Faro, it can even be observed that by 2030, an average performance close to the 'ideal' case of a fully retrofitted building stock can be obtained.

3.4. Assessment of the integrated retrofitting

In this paragraph the benefits of a simultaneous seismic and energy retrofitting are examined. The combined seismic and energy performance of buildings is evaluated using as an index the sum of energy and seismic *EAL* classified in the performance levels proposed in [24] and applied also in [19,33]. The building stocks in all case study locations are assessed in their 2011 state and compared to the prospected building stock in 2030 following the optimal ren-

Fig. 13. Total heating and cooling energy demand per city for the current building stock and the building stock in 2030.

ovation strategy. The classification from F to A+ is done in terms of combined expected annual losses *EAL_C* (in % of the building value) and allows an insight onto the effect of different seismic risk scenarios and climatic conditions. Values of *EAL_C* above 4.5% correspond to a category F, while a value below 0.5% of annual losses

Fig. 14. Average combined classification of the building stock across all seismic and climatic zones.

Fig. 15. Payback periods for all building ages (average taken over the four climate zones) for the energy retrofit compared to combined and separate seismic and energy retrofitting shown for each Seismic Zone.

corresponds to an A+ rating. The scale follows the categorisation of Calvi et al. [24] and is shown in Fig. 14.

As shown in Fig. 14, the increase in seismic risk (going from seismic zone 1 to 5) within the same climatic zone, leads to an increase of the EAL due to the corresponding increase in the seismic EAL_S . For the low seismic risk zones, i.e. where the EAL is dominated by losses from energy costs, the hottest climates show the highest losses. This can be related to the higher cooling costs compared to heating costs per kWh, as well as the disproportionately

higher building value compared to heating and cooling costs in the colder zones. In the higher seismic risk zones, the highest losses are observed in climatic zone 3, which can be associated to the relatively old building stock in the specific case study locations in Italy, compared to building stocks with more modern construction as in Greece for climatic zones 1 and 2. Most importantly, a trend observable for all combinations of seismic and climatic zones is the reduction of at least one category in terms of combined seismic and energy classes for the average building stock.

Finally, the impact of the renovation strategy in terms of cost benefits for each seismic zone is evaluated by comparing the savings in terms of energy costs and seismic losses with the initial investment costs by means of assessing the payback periods, calculated using Eq. 5. As mentioned initially, the effect of combined seismic and energy retrofitting is evaluated in this study and seismic risk mitigation should be considered according to the new Energy Performance of Buildings Directive [2]. The plots in Fig. 15 allow to assess whether a combined retrofit is worthwhile compared to an energy retrofit alone for each building type and seismic zone. The average of the payback periods in the four cities (i.e. four climate zones) is calculated for each seismic zone. The payback periods of separate seismic and energy intervention are also indicated.

The exact values of payback periods should be considered rather preliminary in nature, as further analysis of the financial aspects are required, in particular with more detailed seismic loss modelling and cost estimations. Still, the results shown herein indicate important trends regarding the benefits of combined retrofit interventions. For locations of low seismicity (seismic zones 1 and 2), the effect of adding seismic retrofitting is generally not beneficial and the payback period is lower for energy retrofitting alone than the combined retrofitting scenario. However, when assessing locations in zones of medium to high seismicity (seismic zones 3 to 5), the benefits of providing simultaneously the seismic and energy retrofitting are illustrated, as in these zones the importance of seismic loss reduction becomes more critical than the energy savings alone. The benefits are particularly important for older buildings, as losses due to energy costs and due to seismic events can be significantly reduced. Even for seismic zone 2, with low seismic hazard, the combined retrofit payback period is significantly reduced for the oldest masonry and RC buildings, i.e. buildings designed without seismic guidelines. Importantly, for zones in which seismic retrofit are essential (i.e. above seismic zone 3), doing the seismic intervention separately from the energy retrofit, will lead to longer payback periods. It is hence shown that combined retrofitting is recommendable in these cases.

4. Conclusions

The poor energy performance of the existing building stock in combination with the current low renovation rates make it challenging to meet the ambitious energy saving and decarbonisation targets for 2030 and beyond for the European building stock. Increasing the renovation rate across Europe has hence been recognised as an important target within the European Green Deal, which is however associated to costs and technical limitations. Moreover, natural or man-made risks, such as fire or earthquakes may result in losing initial investments in energy retrofitting, which has recently been recognised by the amended EBPD.

Looking at building renovation from a holistic point of view, considering energy performance, but also structural retrofitting for instance in areas of seismic risk, is starting to gain traction in the academic literature. The effect of such a combined retrofit on the energy performance of the European building stock was assessed in this study. Building typologies simulating both the thermal and seismic performance of typical European structures were defined, and their energy performance was assessed in twenty case study cities across Europe for different levels of seismic hazard and climatic conditions. An adequate energy retrofit target and intervention level was initially assessed, finding that retrofitting the external building skin can achieve reductions of about 70% in heating and cooling energy demand.

By combining the results for the building stock in the considered case study locations, the effect of four renovation strategies was evaluated and their impact on energy efficiency and CO₂-emissions was assessed. For the current annual renovation rate of

around 1%, the ambitious targets for energy reduction are not going to be achieved. If renovation rates are increased to 3%, in particular when starting with the oldest building typologies first, the energy use for heating and cooling may be reduced by up to 32.5%. This would lead to reductions of around 30% in CO₂ emissions across all cities to be achieved by 2030, with reductions ranging from 26.8 to 37.7%, due to a more homogenous energy performance of the building stock

When using a combined monetary metric, namely expected annual loss, for energy and seismic performance across the locations, significant improvements leading to average reductions of at least one category in terms of combined seismic and energy classes for the building stock were obtained. The implementation of an increased renovation rate was shown not only to achieve the emission reduction targets, but to also be economically efficient, as reduced losses from energy costs and seismic damage make the renovation strategies more viable. Looking at payback periods for the combined energy and seismic retrofit investment, already in low seismicity zones, integrated interventions started showing financial benefits over energy retrofitting alone. In zones in which seismic retrofitting is essential due to higher seismic activity, performing the combined retrofit at once instead of separate interventions, showed significant reduction in the intervention's payback period.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

D.A. Pohoryles: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Visualization, Writing - original draft. **C. Maduta:** Methodology, Software, Investigation, Validation, Writing - review & editing. **D.A. Bournas:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **L.A. Kouris:** Writing - review & editing, Formal analysis.

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Supplementary materials

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Appendix A - Thermo-Technical Characteristics Of The Building Elements And Materials

A.1. Masonry buildings

The windows are assumed to be double pane with a wooden frame system with a total U-factor of 3.2 W/ (m²K) and the solar heat gain coefficient of 0.85.

Table A.1

Thermo-technical characteristics for external walls of pre – 1945 stone masonry buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat c (J/kgK)
External Plaster (lime mortar)	0.020	0.720	1600	840
Masonry (rubble + lime joint mortar)*	0.450	2.030	2300	920
Internal Plaster(lime mortar)	0.020	0.720	1600	840
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W**	0.445			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	2.25			

* assuming 60% rubble and 40% joint mortar

Table A.2

Thermo-technical characteristics for external walls of pre – 1945 brick masonry buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat c (J/kgK)
External Plaster (lime mortar)	0.020	0.720	1600	840
Masonry (solid clay brick + lime joint mortar)*	0.450	0.820	1800	870
Internal Plaster(lime mortar)	0.020	0.720	1600	840
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W**	0.772			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	1.30			

* assuming 80% brick and 20% joint mortar.

Table A.3

Thermo-technical characteristics for the roofs of pre – 1945 masonry buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat c (J/kgK)
Interior finishing (wooden planks)	0.01	0.19	550	2510
Structural elements (wooden beams and planks)	0.03	0.23	800	2510
Exterior finishing(terracotta tiles)	0.01	1.00	2100	920
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W**	0.433			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	2.31			

** The superficial internal and external thermal resistances were considered in the total R-value of the envelope elements, as following: 0.125 and 0.043 (m²K)/W for walls and 0.125 and 0.084 (m²K)/W for roof.**Table A.4**

Thermo-technical characteristics for the attic of pre – 1945 masonry buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat c (J/kgK)
Floor finishing(wooden planks)	0.02	0.190	550	2510
Structural elements(wooden beams + planks)	0.01	0.190	550	2510
Ceiling finishing (lime - mortar)	0.02	0.720	1600	840
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W	0.339			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	2.95			

Table A.5

Thermo-technical characteristics for the slab on ground for pre – 1945 masonry buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat c (J/kgK)
Floor finishing(wooden tiles)	0.02	0.190	550	2510
Bedding mortar	0.01	0.190	550	2510
Rubble drain	0.02	0.720	1600	840
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W	0.446			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	2.24			

A.2. RC buildings

The windows are assumed to be double pane with a wooden frame with a total U-factor of 2.8 W/ (m²K) and the solar heat gain coefficient of 0.75.

Table A.6

Thermo-technical characteristics for external walls of 1945 -1959 infilled RC buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific heat c (J/kgK)
External Plaster (lime - cement mortar)	0.015	0.896	1700	840
Masonry (solid clay brick + joint mortar)*	0.300	0.824	2150	870
Internal Plaster(lime - cement mortar)	0.015	0.896	1700	840
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W**	0.565			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	1.77			

* brick dimensions 250×120×65, joint mortar thickness 10–12 mm

Table A.7

Thermo-technical characteristics for external walls of 1960 -1969 infilled RC buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific heat c (J/kgK)
External Plaster (lime - cement mortar)	0.015	0.896	1700	840
Masonry (hollow clay brick + joint mortar)*	0.250	0.302	830	870
Internal Plaster(lime - cement mortar)	0.015	0.896	1700	840
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W**	1.029			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	0.97			

* brick dimensions 250×245×201, volume of brick holes 64%, joint mortar thickness 10–12 mm

Table A.8

Thermo-technical characteristics for external walls of 1970 -1989 infilled RC buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat c (J/kgK)
External Plaster (lime - cement mortar)	0.020	0.896	1700	840
Masonry (hollow clay brick + joint mortar)*	0.120	0.278	840	870
Air cavity	0.050	R = 0.180 (m ² K)/W		
Masonry (hollow clay brick + joint mortar)*	0.120	0.278	840	870
Internal Plaster(lime - cement mortar)	0.020	0.896	1700	840
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W**	1.255			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	0.79			

* brick dimensions 250×120×275, volume of brick holes > 65%, joint mortar thickness 10–12 mm

Table A.9

Thermo-technical characteristics for the roofs of infilled RC buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat c (J/kgK)
Light weight concrete for slope	0.03	1.710	2100	840
RC slab	0.15	2.170	2500	840
Plaster(lime - cement mortar)	0.02	0.896	1700	840
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W**	0.316			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	3.16			

** The superficial internal and external thermal resistances were considered in the total R-value of the envelope elements, as following: 0.125 and 0.043 (m²K)/W for walls and 0.125 and 0.084 (m²K)/W for roof.**Table A.10**

Thermo-technical characteristics for the slab on ground of infilled RC buildings.

Layers (material)	Thicknessd (m)	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Specific Heat c (J/kgK)
RC slab	0.150	2.170	2500	840
Floor finishing (wooden tiles)	0.012	0.200	650	2150
R- value (thermal resistance) (m ² K)/W	0.289			
U- value (thermal transmittance) W/ (m ² K)	3.46			

Appendix B – Cost and energy data

Table B.1

– Data for energy factors and costs for each location.

Location	f_{Ptot}^*	$k_{\text{CO}_2\text{e}}^*$	2020 f_{Ptot}	2020 $k_{\text{CO}_2\text{e}}$	2030 f_{Ptot}	2030 $k_{\text{CO}_2\text{e}}$	Heat cost (gas)	Cool cost (electr.)	Constr. cost index	Building value
	[104]	[104]	[105]	[105]	[105]	[105]	[106]	[107]	[117]	[108]
		g/kWh		g/kWh		g/kWh	€/kWh	€/kWh		€/m ²
Faro	1.45	212.0	1.41	191.9	1.41	175.4	0.0784	0.2293	50.33	1650.0
Larnaca	1.28	205.4	1.24	185.3	1.23	168.8	0.0784	0.2183	60.29	1050.0
Lisbon	1.45	212.0	1.41	191.9	1.41	175.4	0.0784	0.2293	50.33	2290.3
Seville	1.30	219.2	1.26	199.1	1.26	182.6	0.0875	0.2477	70.52	1366.6
Athens	1.43	239.2	1.39	219.1	1.39	202.6	0.0654	0.1646	63.46	1674.9
Porto	1.45	212.0	1.41	191.9	1.41	175.4	0.0784	0.2293	50.33	1493.5
Rome	1.27	205.2	1.23	185.1	1.23	168.6	0.0951	0.2161	93.63	2958.7
Bari	1.27	205.2	1.23	185.1	1.23	168.6	0.0951	0.2161	93.63	2180.0
Thessalon.	1.43	239.2	1.39	219.1	1.39	202.6	0.0654	0.1646	63.46	1262.0
Istanbul	1.43	239.2	1.39	219.1	1.39	202.6	0.0209	0.0857	68.00	691.1
Perugia	1.27	205.2	1.23	185.1	1.23	168.6	0.0951	0.2161	93.63	1246.0
Milan	1.27	205.2	1.23	185.1	1.23	168.6	0.0951	0.2161	93.63	3407.8
Potenza	1.27	205.2	1.23	185.1	1.23	168.6	0.0951	0.2161	93.63	1246.0
Belgrade	1.49	200.0	1.45	179.9	1.45	163.4	0.0342	0.0709	38.00	1291.9
Geneva	1.33	202.1	1.29	182.0	1.29	165.5	0.0951	0.2477	137.42	8426.9
Bucharest	1.19	141.2	1.15	121.0	1.14	104.5	0.0354	0.1317	46.40	1081.6
Sofia	1.49	200.0	1.45	179.9	1.45	163.4	0.0437	0.1005	48.69	981.7
Bratislava	1.36	257.4	1.32	237.3	1.32	220.8	0.0459	0.1462	51.68	2135.4
Groningen	1.19	220.2	1.15	200.0	1.14	183.5	0.0861	0.1707	82.00	2400.0
Warsaw	1.24	265.7	1.20	245.5	1.20	229.0	0.0450	0.1396	65.61	2010.6

* The cooling primary energy factor, f_{Ptot} , is 2.5 and the associated factor for equivalent operational CO₂ emissions ($k_{\text{CO}_2\text{e}}$ in g/kWh) proposed in ISO 52000-1 is 420 g/kWh.

B.1. Masonry buildings

Table B.2– Mean value μ of the lognormal distribution functions per damage state (DS) of the fragility of masonry buildings [109,118].

Damage State	Description	Pre-1945			Retrofitted (confined masonry)		
		Stone	Brick Low-rise	Brick Mid-rise	Stone	Brick Low-rise	Brick Mid-rise
DS1	Slight	0.085	0.184	0.135	0.270	0.368	0.246
DS2	Moderate	0.107	0.230	0.170	0.368	0.565	0.454
DS3	Substantial	0.152	0.304	0.205	0.614	1.141	0.994
DS4	Very heavy	0.152	0.304	0.205	0.614	1.141	0.994
DS5	Collapse	0.179	0.318	0.224	1.043	1.927	2.332

Table B.3– Standard deviation σ of the lognormal distribution functions per damage state (DS) of the fragility of masonry buildings [109,118].

Damage State	Description	Pre-1945			Retrofitted (confined masonry)		
		Stone	Brick Low-rise	Brick Mid-rise	Stone	Brick Low-rise	Brick Mid-rise
DS1	Slight	0.055	0.115	0.085	0.192	0.262	0.175
DS2	Moderate	0.070	0.145	0.106	0.262	0.402	0.323
DS3	Substantial	0.071	0.194	0.119	0.437	0.812	0.707
DS4	Very heavy	0.071	0.194	0.119	0.437	0.812	0.707
DS5	Collapse	0.066	0.196	0.113	0.742	1.371	1.659

B.2. RC buildings

Table B.4– Mean value μ of the lognormal distribution functions per damage state (DS) of the fragility of infilled RC buildings [49].

DS	1945–1959: no seismic design			1960–1969: low seismic design			1970–1989: medium seismic design			Post-1989: high seismic design		
	Low -rise	Mid-rise	High-rise	Low -rise	Mid-rise	High-rise	Low -rise	Mid-rise	High-rise	Low -rise	Mid-rise	High-rise
DS1	0.021	0.005	0.013	0.119	0.034	0.078	0.090	0.008	0.017	0.146	0.120	0.114
DS2	0.101	0.055	0.097	0.241	0.181	0.230	0.123	0.078	0.109	0.359	0.248	0.319
DS3	0.201	0.190	0.210	0.300	0.251	0.309	0.298	0.201	0.419	0.923	0.484	0.978
DS4	0.257	0.216	0.296	0.393	0.290	0.439	0.730	0.422	0.923	2.137	1.041	1.884
DS5	0.343	0.254	0.548	0.540	0.346	1.505	1.391	0.853	3.471	2.793	2.066	5.504

Table B.5– Standard deviation σ of the lognormal distribution functions per damage state (DS) of the fragility of infilled RC buildings [49].

DS	1945–1959: no seismic design			1960–1969: low seismic design			1970–1989: medium seismic design			Post-1989: high seismic design		
	Low -rise	Mid-rise	High-rise	Low -rise	Mid-rise	High-rise	Low -rise	Mid-rise	High-rise	Low -rise	Mid-rise	High-rise
DS1	0.733	0.651	0.629	0.100	0.025	0.055	0.733	0.651	0.629	0.119	0.084	0.076
DS2	0.733	0.651	0.629	0.203	0.132	0.161	0.733	0.651	0.629	0.293	0.173	0.213
DS3	0.733	0.651	0.629	0.253	0.182	0.215	0.733	0.651	0.629	0.752	0.337	0.653
DS4	0.733	0.651	0.629	0.331	0.211	0.306	0.733	0.651	0.629	1.742	0.726	1.257
DS5	0.733	0.651	0.629	0.455	0.251	1.049	0.733	0.651	0.629	2.277	1.441	3.674

Table B.6

– Values for the damage-to-loss functions from for masonry and RC buildings [49]

		Loss (ratio of building value)	
DS	Description	Masonry	Infilled RC
DS1	Slight	0.020	0.005
DS2	Moderate	0.120	0.050
DS3	Substantial	0.350	0.200
DS4	Very heavy	0.350	0.450
DS5	Collapse	0.750	0.800

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